

Seven new records for the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) fauna of Kosovo

Devrim Baymak^{1*} Suat Kiyak²

¹National Institute of Public Health of Kosova, 10000 Nëna Tereze, Pristina, KOSOVA

²Gazi Universty, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology,
06500 Teknikokullar, Ankara, TURKEY

E-mail: skiyak@gazi.edu.tr ORCID iD: 0000-0001-8167-8283 (SK)

ABSTRACT: This study, in which new records were given from Kosovo, was made on the basis of 28 specimens of 7 species of 7 genera in 4 families in the suborder Heteroptera (Hemiptera) in Kosovo. This seven species given in this study are; Lygaeidae: *Spilostethus pandurus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Gastrodes grossipes* (De Geer, 1773) and *Scolopostethus grandis* (Horvath, 1880); Rhopalidae: *Stictopleurus abutilon* (Rossi, 1790); Coreidae: *Enoplops disciger* (Kolenati, 1845); Scutelleridae: *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (Rossi, 1790) and *Eurygaster maura* (Linnaeus, 1758).

The examined material was collected during the field studies in Prizren, Peja, Shtime, Kacanik, Pristina, Dragas, Gjakova and Strpce in Kosovo between 2011-2012.

The distribution of these species in Kosovo were shown on the map .

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, seven new records, fauna, Kosovo .

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INTRODUCTION

The known fauna of Heteroptera species in Kosovo is still in its infancy/ beginning and is usually based on several studies on 19 and 20-century studies. The informations about the Kosovo Heteroptera fauna are records of the work of scientists who were doing research when Kosovo was connected to the former Yugoslavia and former Serbia. (Schumacher, 1918; Horváth, 1903, 1916;

Kormilev, 1936, 1939; Csiki, 1940, Josifov, 1986; Josifov & Simov 2006). The recent studies on the Heteroptera fauna of Kosovo are among the studies carried out by Protic between 1988 and 2011. The latest study of Heteroptera fauna of Kosovo belongs to Baymak & Kiyak (2019) and 6 new records from the country were given. When all these studies are evaluated, the number of known species from Kosovo are 228.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was conducted in Kosovo, a total of 28 adult specimens of seven species were collected from 13 locations in Kosovo from June to September during in 2011-2012 (Figure 1 and Table 1).

The specimens of Heteroptera were collected by an insect trap and killed in 70% alcohol jars and were prepared based on technical and standards of data collection of the zoology museum. These were determined us-

ing identification keys by Stichel (1957-1962), Pehlivan (1981) and Bei-Bienko (1964). In this study was given the provinces of Kosovo where new faunistic records of seven species belonging to four families of the suborder Heteroptera collected and recorded (Table 2). The distribution of the species is marked on the map (Figure 1).

All samples are deposited in the collection of the Zoological Museum of Gazi University (ZMGU), Ankara, Turkey.

Fig. 1. Study area and localities in the Republic of Kosovo

Table 1. Sampling localities of Heteroptera specimens from Kosovo. Geographical coordinates, sampling date, number of examples (n).

Locality No	Province	Coordinates	Altitude (m)	Sampling Date	n
D1	Prizren	42°12'33.N,20°44'42.E	450-550	22.07.2012	1
D2	Gjakova(Skivjan)	42°25'52.N,20°22'54.E	400-440	23.07.2012	1
D3	Prizren(Musnikov)	42°10'36.N,20°54'31.E	950-1000	24.07.2012	1
D4	Pristina	42°40'3.N,21°13'38.E	700-1000	22.07.2012	2
D5	Prizren (Prevalac)	42°9'42.N,20°54'42.E	1200-1500	24.07.2012	2
D6	Prizren	42°12'22.N,20°45'21.E	400-500	25.07.2012	1
D7	Shtime	42°26'14.N,21°1'23.E	600-650	25.07.2012	1
D8	Peja	42°39'12.N,20°17'26.E	500-550	22.07.2012	2
D9	Kacanik	42°15'24.N,21°13'37.E	500-600	22.07.2012	2
D10	Prizren (Lokvica)	42°9'13.N,20°47'28.E	900-1200	22.07.2012	1
D11	Dragas (Brod)	42°0'2.N,20°41'28.E	1000-1500	30.07.2012	7
D12	Peja	42°38'0.N,20°16'37.E	600-1000	26.06.2012	1
D13	Strpce	42°11'59.N,20°59'5.E	900-1250	28.07.2012	1

RESULTS

New records of Heteroptera fauna in Kosovo are as follows:

Family: Lygaeidae Schilling, 1829

Spilostethus Stal, 1868

Spilostethus pandurus (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined:

Loc. D7, Shtime (Belay) 42°26'14.N, 21°1'23.E, 600-650 m, 25.07.2012; 1♀, 2♂♂, Loc. D8, Peja 42°39'12.N, 20°17'26.E, 500-550 m, 22.07.2012; 2♀♀.

Gastrodes Westwood, 1840

Gastrodes grossipes (De Geer, 1773)

Material examined:

Loc. D5, Prizren (Prevalac) 42° 9'42. N, 20°54'42.E, 1200-1500 m, 24.07.2012; 1♀, 1♂.

Scolopostethus Fieber, 1860

Scolopostethus grandis (Horvath, 1880)

Material examined:

Loc. D2, Gjakova (Skivjan) 42°25'52.N, 20°22'54.E, 400 m, 23.07.2012 1♂.

Family: Rhopalidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Stictopleurus (Schilling, 1827)

Stictopleurus abutilon (Rossi, 1790)

Material examined:

Loc. D13, Strpce 42°11'59.N, 20°59'5.E, 1250 m, 28.07.2012; 1♀, Loc. D4, Pristina 42°40'3.71"K 21°13'38.45"E 700-1000 m, 22.07.2012; 1♀, 1♂.

Family: Coreidae Leach, 1815

Enoplops Amyot & Serville, 1843

Enoplops disciger (Kolenati, 1845)

Material examined:

Loc. D6, Prizren 42°12'22.22"K 20°45'21.14"E, 500 m, 25.07.2012; 1♀.

Family: Scutelleridae Leach, 1815

Odontotarsus Laporte, 1833**Odontotarsus purpureolineatus (Rossi, 1790)****Material examined:**

Loc. D1, Prizren 42°12'33.N 20°44'42.E, 450 m, 22.07.2011; 1♂,

Loc. D7, Shtime (Belay) 42°26'14.N, 21°1'23.E, 600 m, 25.07.2012; 1♂,

Loc. D11, Dragas (Brod) 42° 0'2.N 20° 41'28.E, 1500 m, 30.07.2012; 1♀.

Eurygaster Laporte, 1833**Eurygaster maura (Linnaeus, 1758)****Material examined:**

Loc. D11, Dragas (Brod) 42° 0'2.N 20° 41'28.E, 1000-1500 m, 30.07.2012; 6♀♀, 1♂,

Loc. D9, Kacanik 42°15'24.N, 21°13'37.E, 500-600 m, 22.07.2012; 1♀, 1♂,

Loc. D12, Peja 42°38'0.N, 20° 16'37.E, 1000 m, 26.06.2012; 1♂,

Loc. D10, Prizren (Lokvica) 42° 9'13.N, 20°47'28.E, 900 m, 22.07.2012; 1♀,

Loc. D7, Shtime (Belay) 42°26'14.N, 21°1'23.E, 650 m, 25.07.2012; 1♂, Loc. D3, Prizren (Musnikova) 42°10'36.N, 20° 54'31.E, 950 m, 4.07.2012; 1♂.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study is based on 28 specimens of the four Heteroptera families. The specimens from the following provinces of Kosovo were collected and recorded: Prizren, Gjakova, Pristina, Shtime, Peja, Kacanik, Dragas, Strpce (Table 2).

These have been identified as 7 new faunistic records for Heteroptera from Kosovo.

The newly recorded seven species from Kosovo are **Lygaeidae:** *Spilostethus pandurus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Gastrodes grossipes* (De Geer, 1773) and *Scolopostethus grandis* (Horvath, 1880); **Rhopalidae:** *Stictopleurus abutilon* (Rossi, 1790); **Coreidae:** *Enoplops disciger* (Kolenati, 1845); **Scutelleridae:** *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (Rossi, 1790) and *Eurygaster maura* (Linnaeus, 1758).

The number of species we earlier detected as a result of the literature research in the study area (Kosovo) was 222. With 6 new records (Baymak & Kiyak, 2019) published earlier, the number of species belonging to the fauna of Heteroptera in Kosovo reached 228 species.

Table 2. Heteropteran species recorded from Kosovo provinces.

Province	The name of the Species
Prizren	<i>Gastrodes grossipes</i> (De Geer, 1773), <i>Enoplops disciger</i> (Kolenati, 1845), <i>Odontotarsus purpureolineatus</i> (Rossi, 1790), <i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Gjakova	<i>Scolopostethus grandis</i> (Horvath, 1880)
Pristina	<i>Stictopleurus abutilon</i> (Rossi, 1790)
Shtime	<i>Spilostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763), <i>Odontotarsus purpureolineatus</i> (Rossi, 1790)
Peja	<i>Spilostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763), <i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Kacanik	<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Dragas	<i>Odontotarsus purpureolineatus</i> (Rossi, 1790), <i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Strpce	<i>Stictopleurus abutilon</i> (Rossi, 1790)

With the 7 species we recorded with this study, the Kosovo Heteroptera fauna reached 235 species.

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